

A Study of Public Health Indicators of Morang Nepal by Lot Quality Assurance Sampling Method

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ABSTRACT

This article presents the findings of public health status indicators of Morang District as studied by Lot Quality Assurance Sampling (LQAS) methods 2006. The contraceptive prevalence rate (CPR) and women receiving antenatal service from health workers were 42.0% and 46.0%, respectively. A total of 80.0% mothers were receiving iron tablets whereas 55.0% mothers gave history of taking Vita A during their last pregnancy. Nearly three-fifth (57.0%) of deliveries was conducted by health workers. Thirty-one percent of mothers fed their breast milk within 1 hour during last natal period. These figures were higher compared with previous years.

Keywords: LQAS, health indicators, Morang District, Nepal.

INTRODUCTION

Morang, one of the Terai districts in Eastern Development Region (EDR), is comprised of 65 VDCs where 66 governmental health institutions are providing primary health care services. According to the UNDP report 2001,¹ human development index of the district is better among the districts in EDR. Health management information system (HMIS) has reported the coverage. However, all indicators necessary for planning process do not come from the HMIS.² There has been both over reporting and under reporting.³ A descriptive cross sectional study is helpful to evaluate the situation of services and reporting status. Lot Quality Assurance Sampling (LQAS) method with random sampling gives us overall situation of a district. The objective of survey was to assess the behavior and practice related to health related issues in the community. In this paper, we report the status of ANC/NC/PNC service, immunization of children and mother, utilization of family planning services, primary health care out reach clinic (PHC-ORC), health facility management committee (HFMC) and infection prevention practice at health facilities.

METHODS

Study design: It is a descriptive study of cross-sectional type. Primary data collection by interviews with mothers, health workers, members of committees from randomly selected sites using questionnaires. Structured questionnaire were filled up by enumerator after having training. All data collected from questionnaire were entered into computer and processed using SPSS software. All precaution measures to prevent data entry errors were undertaken.

Study Population: A defining characteristic of LQAS uses a sample size of 19 for each SA. In this LQAS described by *Joseph J. Vadez, William Weiss, Corey Leburg, Robb Davis* state that randomly selected 19 samples from divided supervision areas is sufficient to distinguish between high and low coverage.⁴ Samples were taken as- 1. Married women having children of 12 to 23 months (n= 133), 2. Members of PHC-ORC (n=55), 3. Members of HFMC (n=63), 4. Health facilities staff for infection prevention practices (n=63).

Supervision Areas: As per described by LQAS method district has been divided into seven supervision areas (SAs). The total number of 65 VDCs divided into 6 supervision areas as 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6. Biratnagar Sub Metropolitan city has been taken as a supervision area 7. SAs were **SA-1:** Urlabari, Pathari, Sanischare, Rajghat, Hoklabari, Keraun, and Bayarban VDCs; **SA-2:** Itahara, Amardaha, Govindapur, Jhurkia, Sijuwa, Bardanga, Mahadewa, Hasandaha, Takuwa, amgachi, and Dainia VDCs; **SA-3:** Jhorahat, Bhaudaha, Indrapur, Belbari, Haraicha, Dangihat, Kaseni, Bahuni, Sidraha, Thalaha, Banigama and Motipur VDCs; **SA-4:** Sundarpur, Dulari, Mrigaulia, Hattimudha, Siswani Badahara, Baijanathpur, Tanki, Lakhantari, Dangraha, Katahari and Siswani Jahada VDCs; **SA-5:** Budhnagar, Darbesa, Babiabirta, Sorabhag, Bhatigach, Dadarbairia, Kadmaha, Amahi, Majhare, Nocha, Pokharia and Rangeli VDCs; **SA-6:** Letang, Jante, Bhogateni, Warangi, Kerabari, Pati, Yangsila, Singhadevi, Madhumalla, Tandi, and Ramite VDCs and **SA-7:** Biratnagar Sub Metropolitan City Ward No. 1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 10, 11, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, and 22.

RESULTS

Table-1 shows the percentage of monthly meetings held, committees addressing at least three health management issues, health institutions having updated financial records and the proportion of PHC-ORC those met all three criteria viz monthly meetings within last 3 months, addressing at least three management issues and having updated financial records and reports.

Table-2 shows the increase in clinics run on schedule. ORC management committee's meeting with written minute has also been remarkably increased together with the increase in all essential services provided by ORC. Proportion of PHC-ORC meeting all three criteria viz clinics running on schedule, meeting held with recorded minutes, and clinics providing all essential services package as per protocol has also been improved.

Table-3 shows the increase in sterilization practice. Similarly, disposal of sharps and wastage also increased remarkably. The proportion of health institutions having punctured proof containers and health workers who wash their hands with soap water also increased.

Table-4 shows the increased rate of contraceptive use. Percentage of women having 4 ANC by health workers and mothers receiving iron tablets and vitamin A during last pregnancy was found to be increased. Practices of breast feeding also been improved. Percentage of mother feeding breast milk within 1 hour during last natal period and delivery conducted by health workers also increased. It is note worthy that the proportion of delivery conducted by skilled health workers was increased.

DISCUSSION

Coverage is the percentage of people in any given area (a catchments area or supervision area) who know of and/or practice a recommended health behavior or who receive a particular service. Measles coverage of 91.0% reported by DPHO/HMIS 2062/63⁸ was found to be increased to 93.0% in LQAS 2006. The CPR reported as of 69.6% earlier was found to be only 42.0% in LQAS 2006. SA 6 (*Letang, Jante, Bhogateni, Warangi, Kerabari, Pati, Yangsila, Singhadevi, Madhumalla, Tandi* and *Ramite* VDCs) had relatively low CPR according to decision rule. The percentage of women having four ANC by health workers was 45.7% which was higher than reported earlier. However, SA 6 had comparatively poor coverage of fourth ANC visits. The percentage of mothers receiving iron tablets during last pregnancy and vitamin A in LQAS 2004 (Ref) were found to be increased in LQAS 2006. Complete immunization or measles vaccination was 92.9% as recorded by observing card and history taking. SA 4 (*Indrapur, Dulari, Mrigaulia, Tetaria, Hattimudha, Siswani Badahara, Baijanathpur, Tanki, Lakhantari, Dangraha, Katahari* and *Siswani Jahada* VDCs) had relatively poor immunization coverage. Delivery conducted by health workers also found to be increased as compared with previous survey. In Jhapa District, the delivery conducted by health workers was 21.8% in 2004⁹ and 27.6% in 2006.¹⁰ In Sunsari District, the delivery conducted by health workers was 13.2% in 2004¹¹ and 31.0% in 2006.¹²

These findings showed that the status of public health program coverage in the Morang District is increasing year by year resulting into decreasing infant mortality rate¹³ despite of low level of coverage rate in SA 4 and 6. The SA 4 and 6, therefore, draw attention of managers at both district and community level. Data with regard to EPI and safe motherhood program were in agreement with the DoHS/HMIS data.¹⁴ However, the data regarding CPR and delivery conducted by health workers in district varies remarkably. This might be due to the under reporting of delivery conducted by health workers¹⁵ as this survey has also found that 56.7% deliveries were conducted health workers. Morang District has reported remarkably higher CPR (69.6%) which was only 42.1% in LQAS 2006. It might be due to the proportion of CYP which is mainly occupied by VSC and most of the clients are coming from adjoining districts as well as from India. However, findings of surveys have opened rooms for further assessment especially on the indicators as CPR and delivery conducted by health workers. Such types of LQAS surveys at regular interval are needed to evaluate and improve the district health system.

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Table-1: Comparison of major indicators between LQAS 2004⁵ and 2006 (%)

SN	Indicators	LQAS 2004	LQAS 2006	Trend
1	Monthly Meetings (within last 3 months)	49.1	96.4	+
2	Addressed at least three health management issues	41.8	73.1	+
3	Having updated financial records and reports	88.5	92.2	+
4	Presence of above 1, 2,3	42.0	64.1	P=0.00 29

Table -2: PHC-Out Reach Clinic

SN	Indicators	LQAS 2004	LQAS 2006	Trend
1	ORC running on schedule	87.8	91.6	+
2	Meeting with minute (within last 3 months)	9.5	36.1	+
3	Provided all essential services as per protocol	41.9	56.2	+
4	ORC functioning with 1, 2,3	9.0	18.1	P=0.0978

Table-3: Infection prevention (%)

SN	Indicators	LQAS 2004	LQAS 2006	Trend
1	Sterilization using functioning or boiling pot with cover	70.9	92.1	+
2	Disposal of sharp instruments and medical wastage properly	46.2	94.2	+
3	Having puncture proof container	90.9	97.0	+
4	Wash hands with soap and water	92.6	94.1	+
5	IP Functioning with above 1, 2,3	46.1	68.3	P=0.0027

Table-4: Maternal and child health status over LQAS 2004 and 2006

SN	Indicators	LQAS 2004 (Weighted Average)	LQAS 2006 (Weighted Average)	Trend
1	Contraceptive Prevalence Rate	41.1	42.1	+
2	% of women having 4 ANC by Health Workers	41.9	45.7	+
3	% of mothers who received iron tablets during last pregnancy	70.2	80.1	+
4	% of mothers who received Vita A during last pregnancy	45.1	55.1	+
5	Complete Immunization (Card+ history)	90.3	92.9	+
6	% of mother who fed breast milk within 1 hr during last natal period	24.1	31.3	+
7	% of mothers who received iron tablets during last PN period	32.4	37.7	+
8	% of delivery conducted by skilled health workers	38.0	43.4	+
9	% of delivery conducted by HA, AHW, TTBA, VHW	17.0	13.3	-
10	% of delivery conducted by health workers	52.5	56.7	+